

e-Open Maps, *e*-Closed Maps and *e*-Homeomorphisms in *N*-Neutrosophic Crisp Topological Spaces

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Abstract. The concept of $N_{nc}eO$ and $N_{nc}eC$ mappings in $N_{nc}ts$ are introduced and studied some of their related properties in this article. In addition, $N_{nc}eHom$, $N_{nc}eCHom$ and $N_{nc}eT_{\frac{1}{2}}$ -space in $N_{nc}ts$ are discussed and establishes some of their related characterizations.

Keywords: $N_{nc}e$ -open map, $N_{nc}e$ -closed map, $N_{nc}eT_{\frac{1}{2}}$ -space, $N_{nc}e$ -homeomorphism, $N_{nc}e$ -C homeomorphism.

1. Introduction

Smarandache [14] defined the neutrosophic set on three component neutrosophic sets (T-Truth, F-Falsehood, I-Indeterminacy). Lellis Thivagar et al. [11] was the first given the geometric existence of N topology and in his paper [10] introduced the notion of N_n -open (closed) sets and N_n continuous in N -neutrosophic topological spaces. The concept of N -neutrosophic crisp topological spaces from neutrosophic crisp topological spaces was first explored and investigated by Al-Hamido [1]. As a generalization of closed sets, e -closed sets were introduced and studied by Ekici [7–9]. In 2020, Vadivel and Sundar introduced the concept of N_{nc} γ -open [15], N_{nc} β -open [16] and N_{nc} δ -open sets [18] and their continuous functions [17, 20, 28]

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and open mappings [19, 21, 22]. The new N_{nc} open sets called N_{nc} e -open sets and its continuous functions are introduced in $N_{nc}ts$ by Vadivel et al. [23–27]. Recently, Das et al. [2–6] introduced b -open sets in different types of neutrosophic topological spaces. In this paper, $N_{nc}e$ open mapping, $N_{nc}e$ closed mapping, $N_{nc}e$ homeomorphism and $N_{nc}e$ -C homeomorphism are introduced and some results in $N_{nc}ts$.

2. Preliminaries

Definition 2.1. [13] Let X be a non-empty set. Then F is called a neutrosophic crisp set (in short, ncs) in X if F has the form $F = (F_{01}, F_{02}, F_{03})$, where F_{01}, F_{02} , and F_{03} are subsets of X , then neutrosophic crisp set of types

- (i) $F_{01} \cap F_{02} = F_{02} \cap F_{03} = F_{03} \cap F_{01} = \phi$
- (ii) $F_{01} \cap F_{02} = F_{02} \cap F_{03} = F_{03} \cap F_{01} = \phi$ and $F_{01} \cup F_{02} \cup F_{03} = X$
- (iii) $F_{01} \cap F_{02} \cap F_{03} = \phi$ and $F_{01} \cup F_{02} \cup F_{03} = X$

Definition 2.2. [13] Let $F = (F_{01}, F_{02}, F_{03}), G = (G_{01}, G_{02}, G_{03}) \in ncs(X)$. Then

- (i) $\phi_n = (\phi, \phi, X)$,
- (ii) $X_n = (X, X, \phi)$,
- (iii) $F \subseteq G$, if $F_{01} \subseteq G_{01}, F_{02} \subseteq G_{02}$ and $F_{03} \supseteq G_{03}$.
- (iv) $F = G$, if $F \subseteq G$ and $F \supseteq G$
- (v) $F^c = (F_{03}, F_{02}^c, F_{01})$
- (vi) $F \cap G = (F_{01} \cap G_{01}, F_{02} \cap G_{02}, F_{03} \cup G_{03})$
- (vii) $F \cup G = (F_{01} \cup G_{01}, F_{02} \cup G_{02}, F_{03} \cap G_{03})$.

Definition 2.3. [12] A neutrosophic crisp topology (briefly, nct) on a non-empty set X is a family Γ of nc subsets of X satisfying the following axioms

- (i) $\phi_n, X_n \in \Gamma$.
- (ii) $F_1 \cap F_2 \in \Gamma \forall F_1 \& F_2 \in \Gamma$.
- (iii) $\bigcup_b F_b \in \Gamma$, for any $\{F_b : b \in K\} \subseteq \Gamma$.

Then (X, Γ) is a neutrosophic crisp topological space (briefly, $ncts$) in X . The Γ elements are called neutrosophic crisp open sets (briefly, $ncos$) in X and its complement is called neutrosophic crisp closed set (briefly, $nccs$).

Definition 2.4. [1] Let X be a non-empty set. Then ${}_{nc}\Psi_1, {}_{nc}\Psi_2, \dots, {}_{nc}\Psi_N$ are N -arbitrary crisp topologies defined on X and the collection $N_{nc}\Psi = \{B \subseteq X : B = (\bigcup_{k=1}^N F_k) \cup (\bigcap_{k=1}^N L_k), F_k, L_k \in {}_{nc}\Psi_k\}$ is called N_{nc} -topology on X if the axioms are satisfied:

- (i) $\phi_n, X_n \in N_{nc}\Psi$.
- (ii) $\bigcup_{k=1}^{\infty} K_k \in N_{nc}\Psi \forall \{K_k\}_{k=1}^{\infty} \in N_{nc}\Psi$.

$$(iii) \bigcap_{k=1}^n K_k \in N_{nc}\Psi \vee \{K_k\}_{k=1}^n \in N_{nc}\Psi.$$

Then $(X, N_{nc}\Psi)$ is called a N_{nc} -topological space (briefly, $N_{nc}ts$) on X . The $N_{nc}\Psi$ elements are called N_{nc} -open sets ($N_{nc}os$) on X and its complement is called N_{nc} -closed sets ($N_{nc}cs$) on X . The elements of X are known as N_{nc} -sets ($N_{nc}s$) on X .

Definition 2.5. [1, 18] Let $(X, N_{nc}\Psi)$ be $N_{nc}ts$ on X and F be a $N_{nc}s$ on X , then the N_{nc} interior of F (briefly, $N_{nc}int(F)$), N_{nc} closure of F (briefly, $N_{nc}cl(F)$), $N_{nc}\delta$ interior of F (briefly, $N_{nc}\delta int(F)$) and $N_{nc}\delta$ closure of F (briefly, $N_{nc}\delta cl(F)$) are defined as

$$N_{nc}int(F) = \cup\{C : C \subseteq F \text{ \& } C \text{ is a } N_{nc}os \text{ in } X\}$$

$$N_{nc}cl(F) = \cap\{D : F \subseteq D \text{ \& } D \text{ is a } N_{nc}cs \text{ in } X\}$$

$$N_{nc}\delta int(F) = \cup\{C : C \subseteq F \text{ \& } C \text{ is a } N_{nc}ros \text{ in } X\}$$

$$N_{nc}\delta cl(F) = \cap\{D : F \subseteq D \text{ \& } D \text{ is a } N_{nc}rcs \text{ in } X\}.$$

Definition 2.6. [1, 15, 18, 26, 28] Let $(X, N_{nc}\Gamma)$ be any $N_{nc}ts$. Let F be a $N_{nc}s$ in $(X, N_{nc}\Psi)$. Then F is said to be a

- (i) N_{nc} -regular (resp. N_{nc} -semi, N_{nc} -pre, N_{nc} - α & N_{nc} - β) open set (briefly, $N_{nc}ros$ (resp. $N_{nc}\mathcal{S}os$, $N_{nc}\mathcal{P}os$, $N_{nc}\alpha os$ & $N_{nc}\beta os$)) if $F = N_{nc}int(N_{nc}cl(F))$ (resp. $F \subseteq N_{nc}cl(N_{nc}int(F))$, $F \subseteq N_{nc}int(N_{nc}cl(F))$, $F \subseteq N_{nc}int(N_{nc}cl(N_{nc}int(F)))$ & $F \subseteq N_{nc}cl(N_{nc}int(N_{nc}cl(F)))$).
- (ii) $N_{nc}\delta$ (resp. $N_{nc}\delta$ -pre, $N_{nc}\delta$ -semi & $N_{nc}e$) open set (briefly, $N_{nc}\delta os$ (resp. $N_{nc}\delta\mathcal{P}os$, $N_{nc}\delta\mathcal{S}os$ & $N_{nc}eos$)) if $F = N_{nc}\delta int(F)$ (resp. $F \subseteq N_{nc}int(N_{nc}\delta cl(F))$, $F \subseteq N_{nc}cl(N_{nc}\delta int(F))$ & $F \subseteq N_{nc}cl(N_{nc}\delta int(F)) \cup N_{nc}int(N_{nc}\delta cl(F))$).

Definition 2.7. [10, 19, 21, 22, 27] Let $(X_1, N_{nc}\Psi)$ and $(X_2, N_{nc}\tau)$ be any two $N_{nc}ts$'s. A map $\zeta : (X_1, N_{nc}\Psi) \rightarrow (X_2, N_{nc}\tau)$ is said to be

- (i) N_{nc} (resp. $N_{nc}\alpha$, N_{nc} semi, N_{nc} pre, $N_{nc}\gamma$, $N_{nc}\beta$, $N_{nc}\delta$, $N_{nc}\delta$ semi & $N_{nc}\delta$ pre)-open mapping (briefly, $N_{nc}O$ (resp. $N_{nc}\alpha O$, $N_{nc}\mathcal{S}O$, $N_{nc}\mathcal{P}O$, $N_{nc}\gamma O$, $N_{nc}\beta O$, $N_{nc}\delta O$, $N_{nc}\delta\mathcal{S}O$ & $N_{nc}\delta\mathcal{P}O$)) if the inverse image of every $N_{nc}os$ in $(X_2, N_{nc}\tau)$ is a $N_{nc}\alpha os$ (resp. $N_{nc}\mathcal{S}os$, $N_{nc}\mathcal{P}os$, $N_{nc}\gamma os$, $N_{nc}\beta os$, $N_{nc}\delta os$, $N_{nc}\delta\mathcal{S}os$ & $N_{nc}\delta\mathcal{P}os$) in $(X_1, N_{nc}\Psi)$.
- (ii) N_{nc} (resp. $N_{nc}\alpha$, N_{nc} semi, N_{nc} pre, $N_{nc}\gamma$, $N_{nc}\beta$, $N_{nc}\delta$, $N_{nc}\delta$ semi & $N_{nc}\delta$ pre)-closed mapping (briefly, $N_{nc}C$ (resp. $N_{nc}\alpha C$, $N_{nc}\mathcal{S}C$, $N_{nc}\mathcal{P}C$, $N_{nc}\gamma C$, $N_{nc}\beta C$, $N_{nc}\delta C$, $N_{nc}\delta\mathcal{S}C$ & $N_{nc}\delta\mathcal{P}C$)) if the inverse image of every $N_{nc}cs$ in $(X_2, N_{nc}\tau)$ is a $N_{nc}\alpha cs$ (resp. $N_{nc}\mathcal{S}cs$, $N_{nc}\mathcal{P}cs$, $N_{nc}\gamma cs$, $N_{nc}\beta cs$, $N_{nc}\delta cs$, $N_{nc}\delta\mathcal{S}cs$ & $N_{nc}\delta\mathcal{P}cs$) in $(X_1, N_{nc}\Psi)$.
- (iii) N_{nc} (resp. $N_{nc}e$)-continuous (briefly, $N_{nc}Cts$ (resp. $N_{nc}eCts$)) if the inverse image of every $N_{nc}os$ in $(X_2, N_{nc}\tau)$ is a $N_{nc}os$ (resp. $N_{nc}eos$) in $(X_1, N_{nc}\Psi)$.
- (iv) N_{nc} -homeomorphism (briefly, $N_{nc}Hom$) if ζ & ζ^{-1} are $N_{nc}Cts$.

Throughout this article, let $(X_1, N_{nc}\Psi)$, $(X_2, N_{nc}\tau)$ and $(X_3, N_{nc}\rho)$ are $N_{nc}ts$'s and $\zeta : (X_1, N_{nc}\Psi) \rightarrow (X_2, N_{nc}\tau)$ and $\eta : (X_2, N_{nc}\tau) \rightarrow (X_3, N_{nc}\rho)$ are mappings.

3. N -Neutrosophic crisp e -open mapping

Definition 3.1. A mapping ζ is N -neutrosophic crisp e -open (briefly, $N_{nc}eO$) if image of every $N_{nc}eos$ of $(X_1, N_{nc}\Psi)$ is $N_{nc}eos$ in $(X_2, N_{nc}\tau)$.

Theorem 3.2. Let ζ be a function. Then Every

- (i) $N_{nc}O$ is a $N_{nc}\alpha O$.
- (ii) $N_{nc}\alpha O$ is a $N_{nc}\mathcal{P}O$.
- (iii) $N_{nc}\mathcal{P}O$ is a $N_{nc}\gamma O$.
- (iv) $N_{nc}\gamma O$ is a $N_{nc}\beta O$.
- (v) $N_{nc}\delta O$ is a $N_{nc}O$.
- (vi) $N_{nc}\delta O$ is a $N_{nc}SO$.
- (vii) $N_{nc}\delta SO$ is a $N_{nc}eO$.
- (viii) $N_{nc}\mathcal{P}O$ is a $N_{nc}\delta\mathcal{P}O$.
- (ix) $N_{nc}\delta\mathcal{P}O$ is a $N_{nc}eO$.
- (x) $N_{nc}eO$ is a $N_{nc}\beta O$.

Proof. Proof of (i) to (iii), (iv) and (v) to (vi) are proved in [19], [21] and [22]. We prove only (vii) to (ix).

(vii) Let ζ be a $N_{nc}\delta SO$ mapping and K is a $N_{nc}os$ in X_1 . Then $\zeta(K)$ is $N_{nc}\delta S os$ in X_2 . Since every $N_{nc}\delta S os$ is $N_{nc}eos$ by Proposition 3.1 in [26], $\zeta(K)$ is $N_{nc}eos$ in X_2 . Therefore ζ is $N_{nc}eO$ mapping.

(viii) Let ζ be a $N_{nc}\mathcal{P}O$ mapping and K is a $N_{nc}os$ in X_1 . Then $\zeta(K)$ is $N_{nc}\mathcal{P}os$ in X_2 . Since every $N_{nc}\mathcal{P}os$ is $N_{nc}\delta\mathcal{P}os$ by Proposition 3.1 in [26], $\zeta(K)$ is $N_{nc}\delta\mathcal{P}os$ in X_2 . Therefore ζ is $N_{nc}\delta\mathcal{P}O$ mapping.

(ix) Let ζ be a $N_{nc}\delta\mathcal{P}O$ mapping and K is a $N_{nc}os$ in X_1 . Then $\zeta(K)$ is $N_{nc}\delta\mathcal{P}os$ in X_2 . Since every $N_{nc}\delta\mathcal{P}os$ is $N_{nc}eos$ by Proposition 3.1 in [26], $\zeta(K)$ is $N_{nc}eos$ in X_2 . Therefore ζ is $N_{nc}eO$ mapping.

(x) Let ζ be a $N_{nc}eO$ mapping and K is a $N_{nc}os$ in X_1 . Then $\zeta(K)$ is $N_{nc}eos$ in X_2 . Since every $N_{nc}eos$ is $N_{nc}\beta os$ by Proposition 3.1 in [26], $\zeta(K)$ is $N_{nc}\beta os$ in X_2 . Therefore ζ is $N_{nc}\beta O$ mapping. \square

Remark 3.3. The following diagram shows $N_{nc}eO$ mapping function in $N_{nc}ts$.

None of these implication is reversible as shown in the following examples.

Example 3.4. Let $X = \{a_o, b_o, c_o, d_o, e_o\} = Y$, $nc\Psi_1 = \{\phi_n, X_n, A_o\}$, $nc\Psi_2 = \{\phi_n, X_n\}$. $A_o = \langle \{a_o\}, \{\phi\}, \{b_o, c_o, d_o, e_o\} \rangle$, then $2_{nc}\Psi = \{\phi_n, X_n, A_o\}$. Let $nc\tau_1 = \{\phi_n, Y_n, B_o, C_o, D_o\}$, $nc\tau_2 = \{\phi_n, Y_n\}$. $B_o = \langle \{c_o\}, \{\phi\}, \{a_o, b_o, d_o, e_o\} \rangle$, $C_o = \langle \{a_o, b_o\}, \{\phi\}, \{c_o, d_o, e_o\} \rangle$, $D_o = \langle \{a_o, b_o, c_o\}, \{\phi\}, \{d_o, e_o\} \rangle$, then $2_{nc}\tau = \{\phi_n, Y_n, B_o, C_o, D_o\}$. Define $\zeta : (X, 2_{nc}\Psi) \rightarrow (Y, 2_{nc}\tau)$ as identity map, then $2_{nc}eO$ map but not $2_{nc}\delta\mathcal{S}O$ map, then $\zeta(\langle \{a_o\}, \{\phi\}, \{b_o, c_o, d_o, e_o\} \rangle) = \langle \{a_o\}, \{\phi\}, \{b_o, c_o, d_o, e_o\} \rangle$ is a $2_{nc}eos$ but not $2_{nc}\delta\mathcal{S}os$ in Y .

Example 3.5. Let $X = \{a_o, b_o, c_o, d_o, e_o\} = Y$, $nc\Psi_1 = \{\phi_n, X_n, A_o\}$, $nc\Psi_2 = \{\phi_n, X_n\}$. $A_o = \langle \{c_o, d_o\}, \{\phi\}, \{a_o, b_o, e_o\} \rangle$, then $2_{nc}\Psi = \{\phi_n, X_n, A_o\}$. Let $nc\tau_1 = \{\phi_n, Y_n, B_o, C_o, D_o\}$, $nc\tau_2 = \{\phi_n, Y_n\}$. $B_o = \langle \{c_o\}, \{\phi\}, \{a_o, b_o, d_o, e_o\} \rangle$, $C_o = \langle \{a_o, b_o\}, \{\phi\}, \{c_o, d_o, e_o\} \rangle$, $D_o = \langle \{a_o, b_o, c_o\}, \{\phi\}, \{d_o, e_o\} \rangle$, then $2_{nc}\tau = \{\phi_n, Y_n, B_o, C_o, D_o\}$. Define $\zeta : (X, 2_{nc}\Psi) \rightarrow (Y, 2_{nc}\tau)$ as identity map, then $2_{nc}eO$ map but not $2_{nc}\delta\mathcal{P}O$ map, then $\zeta(\langle \{c_o, d_o\}, \{\phi\}, \{a_o, b_o, e_o\} \rangle) = \langle \{c_o, d_o\}, \{\phi\}, \{a_o, b_o, e_o\} \rangle$ is a $2_{nc}eos$ but not $2_{nc}\delta\mathcal{P}os$ in Y .

Example 3.6. Let $X = \{a_o, b_o, c_o, d_o, e_o\} = Y$, $nc\Psi_1 = \{\phi_n, X_n, A_o\}$, $nc\Psi_2 = \{\phi_n, X_n\}$. $A_o = \langle \{a_o, d_o\}, \{\phi\}, \{b_o, c_o, e_o\} \rangle$, then $2_{nc}\Psi = \{\phi_n, X_n, A_o\}$. Let $nc\tau_1 = \{\phi_n, Y_n, B_o, C_o, D_o\}$, $nc\tau_2 = \{\phi_n, Y_n\}$. $B_o = \langle \{c_o\}, \{\phi\}, \{a_o, b_o, d_o, e_o\} \rangle$, $C_o = \langle \{a_o, b_o\}, \{\phi\}, \{c_o, d_o, e_o\} \rangle$, $D_o = \langle \{a_o, b_o, c_o\}, \{\phi\}, \{d_o, e_o\} \rangle$, then $2_{nc}\tau = \{\phi_n, Y_n, B_o, C_o, D_o\}$. Define $\zeta : (X, 2_{nc}\Psi) \rightarrow (Y, 2_{nc}\tau)$ as identity map, then $2_{nc}\beta O$ map but not $2_{nc}eO$ map, then $\zeta(\langle \{a_o, d_o\}, \{\phi\}, \{b_o, c_o, e_o\} \rangle) = \langle \{a_o, d_o\}, \{\phi\}, \{b_o, c_o, e_o\} \rangle$ is a $2_{nc}\beta os$ but not $2_{nc}eos$ in Y .

Theorem 3.7. A mapping $\zeta : (X_1, N_{nc}\Psi) \rightarrow (X_2, N_{nc}\tau)$ is $N_{nc}eO$ iff for every $N_{nc}s$ φ of $(X_1, N_{nc}\Psi)$, $\zeta(N_{nc}int(\varphi)) \subseteq N_{nc}eint(\zeta(\varphi))$.

Proof. Necessity: Let ζ be a $N_{nc}eO$ & φ be a $N_{nc}os$ in $(X_1, N_{nc}\Psi)$. Now, $N_{nc}int(\varphi) \subseteq \varphi$ implies $\zeta(N_{nc}int(\varphi)) \subseteq \zeta(\varphi)$. Since ζ is a $N_{nc}eO$, $\zeta(N_{nc}int(\varphi))$ is $N_{nc}eos$ in $(X_2, N_{nc}\tau)$ such that $\zeta(N_{nc}int(\varphi)) \subseteq \zeta(\varphi)$ therefore $\zeta(N_{nc}int(\varphi)) \subseteq N_{nc}eint(\zeta(\varphi))$.

Sufficiency: Assume φ is a $N_{nc}os$ of $(X_1, N_{nc}\Psi)$. Then $\zeta(\varphi) = \zeta(N_{nc}int(\varphi)) \subseteq N_{nc}eint(\zeta(\varphi))$. But $N_{nc}eint(\zeta(\varphi)) \subseteq \zeta(\varphi)$. So $\zeta(\varphi) = N_{nc}eint(\varphi)$ which implies $\zeta(\varphi)$ is a $N_{nc}eos$ of $(X_2, N_{nc}\tau)$ and hence ζ is a $N_{nc}eO$. \square

Theorem 3.8. If $\zeta : (X_1, N_{nc}\Psi) \rightarrow (X_2, N_{nc}\tau)$ is a $N_{nc}eO$ mapping then $N_{nc}int(\zeta^{-1}(\lambda)) \subseteq \zeta^{-1}(N_{nc}eint(\lambda))$ for every $N_{nc}s$ λ of $(X_2, N_{nc}\tau)$.

Proof. Let λ be a $N_{nc}s$ of $(X_2, N_{nc}\tau)$. Then $N_{nc}int(\zeta^{-1}(\lambda))$ is a $N_{nc}os$ in $(X_1, N_{nc}\Psi)$. Since ζ is $N_{nc}eO$, $\zeta(N_{nc}int(\zeta^{-1}(\lambda)))$ is $N_{nc}eo$ in $(X_2, N_{nc}\tau)$ and hence $\zeta(N_{nc}int(\zeta^{-1}(\lambda))) \subseteq N_{nc}eint(\zeta(\zeta^{-1}(\lambda))) \subseteq N_{nc}eint(\lambda)$. Thus $N_{nc}int(\zeta^{-1}(\lambda)) \subseteq \zeta^{-1}(N_{nc}eint(\lambda))$. \square

Theorem 3.9. A mapping $\zeta : (X_1, N_{nc}\Psi) \rightarrow (X_2, N_{nc}\tau)$ is $N_{nc}eO$ iff for each $N_{nc}s$ μ of $(X_2, N_{nc}\tau)$ and for each $N_{nc}cs$ ρ of $(X_1, N_{nc}\Psi)$ containing $\zeta^{-1}(\mu)$ there is a $N_{nc}ecs$ μ of $(X_2, N_{nc}\tau) \ni \mu \subseteq \rho$ & $\zeta^{-1}(\mu) \subseteq \rho$.

Proof. Necessity: Assume ζ is a $N_{nc}eO$. Let μ be the $N_{nc}cs$ of $(X_2, N_{nc}\tau)$ & ρ is a $N_{nc}cs$ of $(X_1, N_{nc}\Psi) \ni \zeta^{-1}(\mu) \subseteq \rho$. Then $\mu = (\zeta^{-1}(\rho^c))^c$ is $N_{nc}ecs$ of $(X_2, N_{nc}\tau) \ni \zeta^{-1}(\mu) \subseteq \rho$.

Sufficiency: Assume ν is a $N_{nc}os$ of $(X_1, N_{nc}\Psi)$. Then $\zeta^{-1}((\zeta(\nu))^c) \subseteq \nu^c$ & ν^c is $N_{nc}cs$ in $(X_1, N_{nc}\Psi)$. By hypothesis there is a $N_{nc}ecs$ μ of $(X_2, N_{nc}\tau) \ni (\zeta(\nu))^c \subseteq \mu$ & $\zeta^{-1}(\mu) \subseteq \nu^c$. Therefore $\nu \subseteq (\zeta^{-1}(\mu))^c$. Hence $\mu^c \subseteq \zeta(\nu) \subseteq \zeta((\zeta^{-1}(\mu))^c) \subseteq \mu^c$ which implies $\zeta(\nu) = \mu^c$. Since μ^c is $N_{nc}eos$ of $(X_2, N_{nc}\tau)$. Hence $\zeta(\nu)$ is $N_{nc}eo$ in $(X_2, N_{nc}\tau)$ and thus ζ is $N_{nc}eO$. \square

Theorem 3.10. A mapping $\zeta : (X_1, N_{nc}\Psi) \rightarrow (X_2, N_{nc}\tau)$ is $N_{nc}eO$ iff $\zeta^{-1}(N_{nc}ecl(\rho)) \subseteq N_{nc}cl(\zeta^{-1}(\rho))$ for every $N_{nc}s$ ρ of $(X_2, N_{nc}\tau)$.

Proof. Necessity: Assume ζ is a $N_{nc}eO$. For any $N_{nc}s$ ρ of $(X_2, N_{nc}\tau)$, $\zeta^{-1}(\rho) \subseteq N_{nc}cl(\zeta^{-1}(\rho))$. Therefore by Theorem 3.9 there exists a $N_{nc}ecs$ μ in $(X_2, N_{nc}\tau) \ni \rho \subseteq \mu$ & $\zeta^{-1}(\mu) \subseteq N_{nc}cl(\zeta^{-1}(\rho))$. Therefore we obtain that $\zeta^{-1}(N_{nc}ecl(\rho)) \subseteq \zeta^{-1}(\mu) \subseteq N_{nc}cl(\zeta^{-1}(\rho))$.

Sufficiency: Assume ρ is a $N_{nc}s$ of $(X_2, N_{nc}\tau)$ & μ is a $N_{nc}cs$ of $(X_1, N_{nc}\Psi)$ containing $\zeta^{-1}(\rho)$. Put $\alpha = N_{nc}cl(\rho)$, then $\rho \subseteq \alpha$ and α is $N_{nc}ec$ & $\zeta^{-1}(\alpha) \subsetneq N_{nc}cl(\zeta^{-1}(\rho)) \subseteq \mu$. Then by Theorem 3.9, ζ is $N_{nc}eO$. \square

Theorem 3.11. If ζ & η be two neutrosophic crisp mappings and $\eta \circ \zeta : (X_1, N_{nc}\Psi) \rightarrow (X_3, N_{nc}\rho)$ is $N_{nc}eO$. If $\eta : (X_2, N_{nc}\tau) \rightarrow (X_3, N_{nc}\rho)$ is $N_{nc}eIrr$ then $\zeta : (X_1, N_{nc}\Psi) \rightarrow (X_2, N_{nc}\tau)$ is $N_{nc}eO$ mapping.

Proof. Let μ be a $N_{nc}os$ in $(X_1, N_{nc}\Psi)$. Then $\eta \circ \zeta(\mu)$ is $N_{nc}eos$ of $(X_3, N_{nc}\rho)$ because $\eta \circ \zeta$ is $N_{nc}eO$. Since η is $N_{nc}eIrr$ & $\eta \circ \zeta(\mu)$ is $N_{nc}eos$ of $(X_3, N_{nc}\rho)$ therefore $\eta^{-1}(\eta \circ \zeta(\mu)) = \zeta(\mu)$ is $N_{nc}eos$ in $(X_2, N_{nc}\tau)$. Hence ζ is $N_{nc}eO$. \square

Theorem 3.12. If ζ is $N_{nc}O$ and η is $N_{nc}eO$ mappings then $\eta \circ \zeta : (X_1, N_{nc}\Psi) \rightarrow (X_3, N_{nc}\rho)$ is $N_{nc}eO$.

Proof. Let μ be a $N_{nc}os$ in $(X_1, N_{nc}\Psi)$. Then $\zeta(\mu)$ is a $N_{nc}os$ of $(X_2, N_{nc}\tau)$ because ζ is a $N_{nc}O$. Since η is $N_{nc}eO$, $\eta(\zeta(\mu)) = (\eta \circ \zeta)(\mu)$ is $N_{nc}eos$ of $(X_3, N_{nc}\rho)$. Hence $\eta \circ \zeta$ is $N_{nc}eO$. \square

4. N -Neutrosophic crisp e -closed mapping

Definition 4.1. A mapping $\zeta : (X_1, N_{nc}\Psi) \rightarrow (X_2, N_{nc}\tau)$ is N -neutrosophic crisp e -closed (briefly, $N_{nc}eC$) if image of every $N_{nc}cs$ of $(X_1, N_{nc}\Psi)$ is $N_{nc}ecs$ in $(X_2, N_{nc}\tau)$.

Theorem 4.2. Let ζ be a function. Then Every

- (i) $N_{nc}C$ is a $N_{nc}\alpha C$.
- (ii) $N_{nc}\alpha C$ is a $N_{nc}PC$.
- (iii) $N_{nc}PC$ is a $N_{nc}\gamma C$.
- (iv) $N_{nc}\gamma C$ is a $N_{nc}\beta C$.
- (v) $N_{nc}\delta C$ is a $N_{nc}C$.
- (vi) $N_{nc}\delta C$ is a $N_{nc}SC$.
- (vii) $N_{nc}\delta SC$ is a $N_{nc}eC$.
- (viii) $N_{nc}PC$ is a $N_{nc}\delta PC$.
- (ix) $N_{nc}\delta PC$ is a $N_{nc}eC$.
- (x) $N_{nc}eC$ is a $N_{nc}\beta C$.

Proof. Proof of (i) to (iii), (iv) and (v) to (vi) are proved in [19], [21] and [22]. We prove only (vii) to (ix).

(vii) Let ζ be a $N_{nc}\delta SC$ mapping and K is a $N_{nc}cs$ in X_1 . Then $\zeta(K)$ is $N_{nc}\delta SCs$ in X_2 . Since every $N_{nc}\delta SCs$ is $N_{nc}ecs$ by Proposition 3.1 in [26], $\zeta(K)$ is $N_{nc}ecs$ in X_2 . Therefore ζ is $N_{nc}eC$ mapping.

(viii) Let ζ be a $N_{nc}PC$ mapping and K is a $N_{nc}cs$ in X_1 . Then $\zeta(K)$ is $N_{nc}PCs$ in X_2 . Since every $N_{nc}PCs$ is $N_{nc}\delta PCs$ by Proposition 3.1 in [26], $\zeta(K)$ is $N_{nc}\delta PCs$ in X_2 . Therefore ζ is $N_{nc}\delta PC$ mapping.

(ix) Let ζ be a $N_{nc}\delta PC$ mapping and K is a $N_{nc}cs$ in X_1 . Then $\zeta(K)$ is $N_{nc}\delta PCs$ in X_2 . Since every $N_{nc}\delta PCs$ is $N_{nc}ecs$ by Proposition 3.1 in [26], $\zeta(K)$ is $N_{nc}ecs$ in X_2 . Therefore ζ is $N_{nc}eC$ mapping.

(x) Let ζ be a $N_{nc}eC$ mapping and K is a $N_{nc}cs$ in X_1 . Then $\zeta(K)$ is $N_{nc}ecs$ in X_2 . Since every $N_{nc}ecs$ is $N_{nc}\beta cs$ by Proposition 3.1 in [26], $\zeta(K)$ is $N_{nc}\beta cs$ in X_2 . Therefore ζ is $N_{nc}\beta C$ mapping. \square

Example 4.3. In Example 3.4, then $2_{nc}eC$ map but not $2_{nc}\delta SC$ map, then $\zeta(\langle\langle\{b_o, c_o, d_o, e_o\}, \{\phi\}, \{a_o\}\rangle\rangle) = \langle\langle\{b_o, c_o, d_o, e_o\}, \{\phi\}, \{a_o\}\rangle\rangle$ is a $2_{nc}ecs$ but not $2_{nc}\delta SCs$.

Example 4.4. In Example 3.5, then $2_{nc}eC$ map but not $2_{nc}\delta PC$ map, then $\zeta(\langle\langle\{a_o, b_o, e_o\}, \{\phi\}, \{c_o, d_o\}\rangle\rangle) = \langle\langle\{a_o, b_o, e_o\}, \{\phi\}, \{c_o, d_o\}\rangle\rangle$ is a $2_{nc}ecs$ but not $2_{nc}\delta PCs$.

Example 4.5. In Example 3.6, then $2_{nc}\beta C$ map but not $2_{nc}eC$ map, then $\zeta(\langle\langle\{b_o, c_o, e_o\}, \{\phi\}, \{a_o, d_o\}\rangle\rangle) = \langle\langle\{b_o, c_o, e_o\}, \{\phi\}, \{a_o, d_o\}\rangle\rangle$ is a $2_{nc}\beta cs$ but not $2_{nc}ecs$.

Remark 4.6. The following diagram shows $N_{nc}eC$ mapping function in $N_{nc}ts$.

None of these implication is reversible as shown in the following examples.

Theorem 4.7. A mapping $\zeta : (X_1, N_{nc}\Psi) \rightarrow (X_2, N_{nc}\tau)$ is $N_{nc}eC$ iff for each $N_{nc}s \mu$ of $(X_2, N_{nc}\tau)$ and for each $N_{nc}os \lambda$ of $(X_1, N_{nc}\Psi)$ containing $\zeta^{-1}(\mu)$ there is a $N_{nc}eos \rho$ of $(X_2, N_{nc}\tau) \ni \mu \subseteq \rho \ \& \ \zeta^{-1}(\rho) \subseteq \lambda$.

Proof. Necessity: Assume ζ is a $N_{nc}eC$. Let μ be the $N_{nc}s$ of $(X_2, N_{nc}\tau)$ & λ is a $N_{nc}os$ of $(X_1, N_{nc}\Psi) \ni \zeta^{-1}(\mu) \subseteq \lambda$. Then $\rho = X_2 - \zeta^{-1}(\lambda^c)$ is $N_{nc}eos$ of $(X_2, N_{nc}\tau) \ni \zeta^{-1}(\rho) \subseteq \lambda$.

Sufficiency: Assume ν is a $N_{nc}s$ of $(X_1, N_{nc}\Psi)$. Then $(\zeta(\nu))^c$ is a $N_{nc}s$ of $(X_2, N_{nc}\tau)$ & ν^c is $N_{nc}os$ in $(X_1, N_{nc}\Psi) \ni \zeta^{-1}((\zeta(\nu))^c) \subseteq \nu^c$. By hypothesis there is a $N_{nc}eos \rho$ of $(X_2, N_{nc}\tau) \ni (\zeta(\nu))^c \subseteq \rho \ \& \ \zeta^{-1}(\rho) \subseteq \nu^c$. Therefore $\nu \subseteq (\zeta^{-1}(\rho))^c$. Hence $\rho^c \subseteq \zeta(\rho) \subseteq \zeta((\zeta^{-1}(\rho))^c) \subseteq \rho^c$ which implies $\zeta(\nu) = \rho^c$. Since ρ^c is $N_{nc}ecs$ of $(X_2, N_{nc}\tau)$. Hence $\zeta(\nu)$ is $N_{nc}ec$ in $(X_2, N_{nc}\tau)$ and thus ζ is $N_{nc}eC$. \square

Theorem 4.8. If ζ is $N_{nc}C$ & η is $N_{nc}eC$. Then $\eta \circ \zeta : (X_1, N_{nc}\Psi) \rightarrow (X_3, N_{nc}\rho)$ is $N_{nc}eC$.

Proof. Let μ be a $N_{nc}s$ in $(X_1, N_{nc}\Psi)$. Then $\zeta(\mu)$ is $N_{nc}s$ of $(X_2, N_{nc}\tau)$ because ζ is $N_{nc}C$. Now $(\eta \circ \zeta)(\mu) = \eta(\zeta(\mu))$ is $N_{nc}ecs$ in $(X_3, N_{nc}\rho)$ because η is $N_{nc}eC$. Thus $\eta \circ \zeta$ is $N_{nc}eC$. \square

Theorem 4.9. If $\zeta : (X_1, N_{nc}\Psi) \rightarrow (X_2, N_{nc}\tau)$ is $N_{nc}eC$ map, then $N_{nc}ecl(\zeta(\rho)) \subsetneq \zeta(N_{nc}cl(\rho))$.

Theorem 4.10. Let ζ & η are $N_{nc}eC$ mappings. If every $N_{nc}ecs$ of $(X_2, N_{nc}\tau)$ is $N_{nc}c$ then, $\eta \circ \zeta : (X_1, N_{nc}\Psi) \rightarrow (X_3, N_{nc}\rho)$ is $N_{nc}eC$.

Proof. Let μ be a $N_{nc}cs$ in $(X_1, N_{nc}\Psi)$. Then $\zeta(\mu)$ is $N_{nc}ecs$ of $(X_2, N_{nc}\tau)$ because ζ is $N_{nc}eC$ mapping. By hypothesis $\zeta(\mu)$ is $N_{nc}cs$ of $(X_2, N_{nc}\tau)$. Now $\eta(\zeta(\mu)) = (\eta \circ \zeta)(\mu)$ is $N_{nc}ecs$ in $(X_3, N_{nc}\rho)$ because η is $N_{nc}eC$. Thus $\eta \circ \zeta$ is $N_{nc}eC$. \square

Theorem 4.11. The following statements are equivalent for a mapping ζ :

- (i) ζ is a $N_{nc}eO$.
- (ii) ζ is a $N_{nc}eC$.
- (iii) ζ^{-1} is $N_{nc}eCts$.

5. N -Neutrosophic crisp e -homeomorphism

Definition 5.1. A bijection ζ is called a $N_{nc}e$ -homeomorphism (briefly $N_{nc}eHom$) if ζ & ζ^{-1} are $N_{nc}eCts$.

Theorem 5.2. Each $N_{nc}Hom$ is a $N_{nc}eHom$.

Proof. Let ζ be $N_{nc}Hom$, then ζ and ζ^{-1} are $N_{nc}Cts$. But every $N_{nc}Cts$ is $N_{nc}eCts$. Hence, ζ and ζ^{-1} is $N_{nc}eCts$. Therefore, ζ is a $N_{nc}eHom$. \square

Theorem 5.3. Let ζ be a bijective mapping. The following statements are equivalent, if ζ is $N_{nc}eCts$:

- (i) ζ is a $N_{nc}eC$.
- (ii) ζ is a $N_{nc}eO$.
- (iii) ζ^{-1} is a $N_{nc}eHom$.

Definition 5.4. A $N_{nc}ts$ $(X_1, N_{nc}\Psi)$ is said to be a neutrosophic crisp $eT_{\frac{1}{2}}$ (briefly, $N_{nc}eT_{\frac{1}{2}}$)-space if every $N_{nc}ecs$ is $N_{nc}c$ in $(X_1, N_{nc}\Psi)$.

Theorem 5.5. Let ζ be a $N_{nc}eHom$, then ζ is a $N_{nc}Hom$ if $(X_1, N_{nc}\Psi)$ and $(X_2, N_{nc}\tau)$ are $N_{nc}eT_{\frac{1}{2}}$ -space.

Proof. Assume that μ is a $N_{nc}cs$ in $(X_2, N_{nc}\tau)$, then $\zeta^{-1}(\mu)$ is a $N_{nc}ecs$ in $(X_1, N_{nc}\Psi)$. Since $(X_1, N_{nc}\Psi)$ is a $N_{nc}eT_{\frac{1}{2}}$ -space, $\zeta^{-1}(\mu)$ is a $N_{nc}cs$ in $(X_1, N_{nc}\Psi)$. Therefore, ζ is $N_{nc}Cts$. By hypothesis, ζ^{-1} is $N_{nc}eCts$. Let ν be a $N_{nc}cs$ in $(X_1, N_{nc}\Psi)$. Then, $(\zeta^{-1})^{-1}(\nu) = \zeta(\nu)$ is a $N_{nc}cs$ in $(X_2, N_{nc}\tau)$, by presumption. Since $(X_2, N_{nc}\tau)$ is a $N_{nc}eT_{\frac{1}{2}}$ -space, $\zeta(\nu)$ is a $N_{nc}cs$ in $(X_2, N_{nc}\tau)$. Hence, ζ^{-1} is $N_{nc}Cts$. Hence, ζ is a $N_{nc}Hom$. \square

Theorem 5.6. The following statements are equivalent for ζ , if $(X_2, N_{nc}\tau)$ is a $N_{nc}eT_{\frac{1}{2}}$ -space:

- (i) ζ is $N_{nc}eC$.

- (ii) If μ is a N_{ncos} in $(X_1, N_{nc}\Psi)$, then $\zeta(\mu)$ is N_{nceos} in $(X_2, N_{nc}\tau)$.
 (iii) $\zeta(N_{ncint}(\mu)) \subseteq N_{nccl}(N_{ncint}(\zeta(\mu)))$ for every N_{ncs} μ in $(X_1, N_{nc}\Psi)$.

Proof. (i) \Rightarrow (ii): Obvious.

(ii) \Rightarrow (iii): Let μ be a N_{ncs} in $(X_1, N_{nc}\Psi)$. Then, $N_{ncint}(\mu)$ is a N_{ncos} in $(X_1, N_{nc}\Psi)$. Then, $\zeta(N_{ncint}(\mu))$ is a N_{nceos} in $(X_2, N_{nc}\tau)$. Since $(X_2, N_{nc}\tau)$ is a $N_{nce}T_{\frac{1}{2}}$ -space, so $\zeta(N_{ncint}(\mu))$ is a N_{ncos} in $(X_2, N_{nc}\tau)$. Therefore, $\zeta(N_{ncint}(\mu)) = N_{ncint}(\zeta(N_{ncint}(\mu))) \subseteq N_{nccl}(N_{ncint}(\zeta(\mu)))$.

(iii) \Rightarrow (i): Let μ be a N_{ncs} in $(X_1, N_{nc}\Psi)$. Then, μ^c is a N_{ncos} in $(X_1, N_{nc}\Psi)$. From, $\zeta(N_{ncint}(\mu^c)) \subseteq N_{nccl}(N_{ncint}(\zeta(\mu^c)))$. Hence, $\zeta(\mu^c) \subseteq N_{nccl}(N_{ncint}(\zeta(\mu^c)))$. Therefore, $\zeta(\mu^c)$ is N_{nceos} in $(X_2, N_{nc}\tau)$. Therefore, $\zeta(\mu)$ is a N_{ncacs} in $(X_1, N_{nc}\Psi)$. Hence, ζ is a N_{ncC} . \square

Theorem 5.7. Let ζ & η be $N_{nc}eC$, where $(X_1, N_{nc}\Psi)$ and $(X_3, N_{nc}\rho)$ are two $N_{nc}ts$'s and $(X_2, N_{nc}\tau)$ a $N_{nce}T_{\frac{1}{2}}$ -space, then the composition $\eta \circ \zeta$ is $N_{nc}eC$.

Proof. Let μ be a N_{ncs} in $(X_1, N_{nc}\Psi)$. Since ζ is $N_{nc}eC$ & $\zeta(\mu)$ is a N_{ncacs} in $(X_2, N_{nc}\tau)$, by assumption, $\zeta(\mu)$ is a N_{ncs} in $(X_2, N_{nc}\tau)$. Since η is $N_{nc}eC$, then $\eta(\zeta(\mu))$ is $N_{nc}eC$ in $(X_3, N_{nc}\rho)$ & $\eta(\zeta(\mu)) = (\eta \circ \zeta)(\mu)$. Therefore, $\eta \circ \zeta$ is $N_{nc}eC$. \square

Theorem 5.8. The following statements are hold for ζ & η :

- (i) If $\eta \circ \zeta$ is $N_{nc}eO$ & ζ is $N_{nc}Cts$, then η is $N_{nc}eO$.
 (ii) If $\eta \circ \zeta$ is $N_{nc}O$ & η is $N_{nc}eCts$, then ζ is $N_{nc}eO$.

Proof. Obvious. \square

6. N -Neutrosophic crisp e -C Homeomorphism

Definition 6.1. A bijection ζ is called a $N_{nc}e$ -C homeomorphism (briefly, $N_{nc}eCHom$) if ζ & ζ^{-1} are $N_{nc}eIrr$ mappings.

Theorem 6.2. Each $N_{nc}eCHom$ is a $N_{nc}eHom$.

Proof. Let us assume that μ is a N_{ncs} in $(X_2, N_{nc}\tau)$. This shows that μ is a N_{ncacs} in $(X_2, N_{nc}\tau)$. By assumption, $\zeta^{-1}(\mu)$ is a N_{ncacs} in $(X_1, N_{nc}\Psi)$. Hence, ζ is a $N_{nc}eCts$. Hence, ζ & ζ^{-1} are $N_{nc}eCts$. Hence ζ is a $N_{nc}eHom$. \square

Theorem 6.3. If $\zeta : (X_1, N_{nc}\Psi) \rightarrow (X_2, N_{nc}\tau)$ is a $N_{nc}eCHom$, then $N_{nc}ecl(\zeta^{-1}(\mu)) \subseteq \zeta^{-1}(N_{nccl}(\mu))$ for each $N_{nc}ts$ μ in $(X_2, N_{nc}\tau)$.

Proof. Let μ be a $N_{nc}ts$ in $(X_2, N_{nc}\tau)$. Then, $N_{nc}cl(\mu)$ is a $N_{nc}cs$ in $(X_2, N_{nc}\tau)$, and every $N_{nc}cs$ is a $N_{nc}ecs$ in $(X_2, N_{nc}\tau)$. Assume ζ is $N_{nc}eIrr$, $\zeta^{-1}(N_{nc}cl(\lambda))$ is a $N_{nc}ecs$ in $(X_1, N_{nc}\Psi)$, then $N_{nc}cl(\zeta^{-1}(N_{nc}cl(\mu))) = \zeta^{-1}(N_{nc}cl(\mu))$. Here, $N_{nc}ecl(\zeta^{-1}(\mu)) \subseteq N_{nc}ecl(\zeta^{-1}(N_{nc}cl(\mu))) = \zeta^{-1}(N_{nc}cl(\mu))$. Therefore, $N_{nc}ecl(\zeta^{-1}(\mu)) \subseteq \zeta^{-1}(N_{nc}cl(\mu))$ for every $N_{nc}s$ μ in $(X_2, N_{nc}\tau)$. \square

Theorem 6.4. Let $\zeta : (X_1, N_{nc}\Psi) \rightarrow (X_2, N_{nc}\tau)$ be a $N_{nc}eCHom$, then $N_{nc}ecl(\zeta^{-1}(\mu)) = \zeta^{-1}(N_{nc}ecl(\mu))$ for each $N_{nc}s$ μ in $(X_2, N_{nc}\tau)$.

Proof. Since ζ is a $N_{nc}eCHom$, then ζ is a $N_{nc}eIrr$. Let μ be a $N_{nc}s$ in $(X_2, N_{nc}\tau)$. Clearly, $N_{nc}ecl(\mu)$ is a $N_{nc}ecs$ in $(X_1, N_{nc}\Psi)$. Then $N_{nc}ecl(\mu)$ is a $N_{nc}ecs$ in $(X_1, N_{nc}\Psi)$. Since $\zeta^{-1}(\mu) \subseteq \zeta^{-1}(N_{nc}ecl(\mu))$, then $N_{nc}ecl(\zeta^{-1}(\mu)) \subseteq N_{nc}ecl(\zeta^{-1}(N_{nc}ecl(\mu))) = \zeta^{-1}(N_{nc}ecl(\mu))$. Therefore, $N_{nc}ecl(\zeta^{-1}(\mu)) \subseteq \zeta^{-1}(N_{nc}ecl(\mu))$. Let ζ be a $N_{nc}eCHom$. ζ^{-1} is a $N_{nc}eIrr$. Let us consider $N_{nc}s$ $\zeta^{-1}(\mu)$ in $(X_1, N_{nc}\Psi)$, which implies $N_{nc}ecl(\zeta^{-1}(\mu))$ is a $N_{nc}ecs$ in $(X_1, N_{nc}\Psi)$. Hence, $N_{nc}ecl(\zeta^{-1}(\mu))$ is a $N_{nc}ecs$ in $(X_1, N_{nc}\Psi)$. This implies that $(\zeta^{-1})^{-1}(N_{nc}ecl(\zeta^{-1}(\mu))) = \zeta(N_{nc}ecl(\zeta^{-1}(\mu)))$ is a $N_{nc}ecs$ in $(X_2, N_{nc}\tau)$. This proves $\mu = (\zeta^{-1})^{-1}(\zeta^{-1}(\mu)) \subseteq (\zeta^{-1})^{-1}(N_{nc}ecl(\zeta^{-1}(\mu))) = \zeta(N_{nc}ecl(\zeta^{-1}(\mu)))$. Therefore, $N_{nc}ecl(\mu) \subseteq N_{nc}ecl(\zeta(N_{nc}ecl(\zeta^{-1}(\mu)))) = \zeta(N_{nc}ecl(\zeta^{-1}(\mu)))$, since ζ^{-1} is a $N_{nc}eIrr$. Hence, $\zeta^{-1}(N_{nc}ecl(\mu)) \subseteq \zeta^{-1}(\zeta(N_{nc}ecl(\zeta^{-1}(\mu)))) = N_{nc}ecl(\zeta^{-1}(\mu))$. That is, $\zeta^{-1}(N_{nc}ecl(\mu)) \subseteq N_{nc}ecl(\zeta^{-1}(\mu))$. Hence, $N_{nc}ecl(\zeta^{-1}(\mu)) = \zeta^{-1}(N_{nc}ecl(\mu))$. \square

Theorem 6.5. If ζ & η are $N_{nc}eCHom$'s, then $\eta \circ \zeta$ is a $N_{nc}eCHom$.

Proof. Let ζ and η to be two $N_{nc}eCHom$'s. Assume μ is a $N_{nc}ecs$ in $(X_3, N_{nc}\rho)$. Then, $\eta^{-1}(\mu)$ is a $N_{nc}ecs$ in $(X_2, N_{nc}\tau)$. Then, by hypothesis, $\zeta^{-1}(\eta^{-1}(\mu))$ is a $N_{nc}ecs$ in $(X_1, N_{nc}\Psi)$. Hence, $\eta \circ \zeta$ is a $N_{nc}eIrr$ mapping. Now, let ν be a $N_{nc}ecs$ in $(X_1, N_{nc}\Psi)$. Then, by presumption, $\zeta(\eta)$ is a $N_{nc}ecs$ in $(X_2, N_{nc}\tau)$. Then, by hypothesis, $\eta(\zeta(\nu))$ is a $N_{nc}ecs$ in $(X_3, N_{nc}\rho)$. This implies that $\eta \circ \zeta$ is a $N_{nc}eIrr$. Hence, $\eta \circ \zeta$ is a $N_{nc}eCHom$. \square

7. Conclusions

In this paper, the new concept of a $N_{nc}eO$ and $N_{nc}eC$ mappings, $N_{nc}Hom$ and a $N_{nc}eHom$ in $N_{nc}ts$ are studied and discussed their properties. Also, we extended to $N_{nc}eCHom$'s and $N_{nc}eT_{\frac{1}{2}}$ -space with some of their properties.

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References

1. Al-Hamido, R.K., Gharibah, T., Jafari, S., & Smarandache, F. (2018). On neutrosophic crisp topology via N -topology. *Neutrosophic Sets and Systems*, 23, 96-109.
2. Das, S., & Pramanik, S. (2020). Generalized neutrosophic b -open sets in neutrosophic topological space. *Neutrosophic Sets and Systems*, 35, 522-530.
3. Das, S., & Pramanik, S. (2020). Neutrosophic simply soft open set in neutrosophic soft topological space. *Neutrosophic Sets and Systems*, 38, 235-243.
4. Das, S., & Tripathy, B. C. (2020). Pairwise neutrosophic- b -open set in neutrosophic bitopological spaces. *Neutrosophic Sets and Systems*, 38, 135-144.
5. Das, S., & Tripathy, B. C. (2021). Neutrosophic simply b -open set in neutrosophic topological spaces. *Iraqi Journal of Science*, In Press
6. Das, S., & Pramanik, S. (2020). Neutrosophic Φ -open sets and neutrosophic Φ -continuous functions. *Neutrosophic Sets and Systems*, 38, 355-367.
7. Ekici, E. (2008). On e -open sets, \mathcal{DP}^* -sets and $\mathcal{DP}\epsilon^*$ -sets and decomposition of continuity. *The Arabian Journal for Science and Engineering*, 33 (2A), 271-282.
8. Ekici, E. (2008). On a -open sets, A^* -sets and decompositions of continuity and super continuity. *Annales Univ. Sci. Budapest*, 51, 39-51.
9. Ekici, E. (2008). New forms of contra continuity. *Bull. Carpathian J. Math.*, 24 (1), 37-45.
10. Lellis Thivagar, M., Jafari, S., Antonysamy, V., & Sutha Devi, V. (2018). The ingenuity of neutrosophic topology via N -topology. *Neutrosophic Sets and Systems*, 19, 91-100.
11. Lellis Thivagar, M., Ramesh, V., & Arockia, M. D. (2016). On new structure of N -topology. *Cogent Mathematics (Taylor and Francis)*, 3, 1204104.
12. Salama, A. A., Smarandache, F., & Kroumov, V. (2014). Neutrosophic crisp sets and neutrosophic crisp topological spaces. *Neutrosophic Sets and Systems*, 2, 25-30.
13. Salama, A. A. & Smarandache, F. (2015). *Neutrosophic crisp set theory*. Educational Publisher, Columbus, Ohio, USA.
14. Smarandache, F. (2002). Neutrosophy and neutrosophic logic. First International Conference on Neutrosophy, Neutrosophic Logic, Set, Probability, and Statistics, University of New Mexico, Gallup, NM 87301, USA.
15. Vadivel, A., & John Sundar, C. (2020). γ -open sets in N_{nc} -topological spaces. *Advances in Mathematics: Scientific Journal*, 9 (4), 2197-2202.
16. Vadivel, A., & John Sundar, C. (2020). $N_{nc}\beta$ -open sets. *Advances in Mathematics: Scientific Journal*, 9 (4), 2203-2207.
17. Vadivel, A., & John Sundar, C. (2022). On Almost γ -Continuous Functions in N -Neutrosophic Crisp Topological Spaces. *Palestine Journal of Mathematics*, 11 (3), 424-432.
18. Vadivel, A., & John Sundar, C. (2022). $N_{nc}\delta$ -Open Sets. *South East Asian Journal of Mathematics and Mathematical Sciences*, 18 (3), 207-216.
19. Vadivel, A., & John Sundar, C. (2022). $N_{nc}\gamma$ Maps in N_{nc} -Topological Spaces. *International Journal of Neutrosophic Science*, 18 (3), 30-40.
20. Vadivel, A., & John Sundar, C. (2023). Some Types of Continuous Function Via N -Neutrosophic Crisp Topological Spaces. *Applications and Applied Mathematics: An International Journal*, 18 (1), 12.
21. Vadivel, A., & John Sundar, C. Some maps on δ -open sets in N_{nc} -topological spaces. Submitted.

P. Thangaraja, A. Vadivel and C. John Sundar, e -Open Maps, e -Closed Maps and e -Homeomorphisms in N -Neutrosophic Crisp Topological Spaces

22. Vadivel, A., John Sundar, C., & Thangaraja, P. Some types of $N_{nc}\beta$ maps in N_{nc} -topological spaces. Submitted.
23. Vadivel, A., Navvluri, M., & Thangaraja, P. (2020). On N_{nc} DP*-sets and decomposition of continuity in N_{nc} -topological spaces. *Advances in Mathematics: Scientific Journal*, 9 (11), 9559-9564.
24. Vadivel, A., Navvluri, M., & Thangaraja, P. (2021). Completely N_{nc} e (weakly N_{nc} e)-irresolute functions via N_{nc} e -open sets. *Journal of Physics: Conference Series*, 1724, 012010.
25. Vadivel, A., Navvluri, M., & Thangaraja, P. (2021). Characterization of completely N_{nc} e (weakly N_{nc} e)-irresolute functions via N_{nc} e -open sets. *Journal of Physics: Conference Series*, 1724, 012009.
26. Vadivel, A., & Thangaraja, P. (2021). e -open sets N_{nc} Topological Spaces. *Journal of Physics: Conference Series*, 1724, 012007.
27. Vadivel, A., & Thangaraja, P. (2021). e -continuous and Somewhat e -continuity in N_{nc} -Topological Spaces. *Journal of Physics: Conference Series*, 1724, 012008.
28. Vadivel, A., Thangaraja, P., & John Sundar, C. (2022). $N_{nc}\beta$ -Continuous Maps. *South East Asian Journal of Mathematics and Mathematical Sciences*, 18 (2), 275-288.

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